

AI4AOP

**An effort to explore the potential of AI
to support the AOP framework**

Thought starter

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1. BACKGROUND

1.1. Adverse Outcome Pathways

Adverse Outcome Pathways (AOPs) are a structured representation of biological events that lead to adverse effects and are considered relevant to risk assessment. AOPs link existing knowledge along a series of causally connected key events (KE) on various levels of biological organisation between two points - a molecular initiating event (MIE) and an adverse outcome (AO), see Figure 1:

Figure 1 - The AOP principle

The OECD Environmental, Health and Safety (EHS) Programme has been helping member countries to make better use of increased knowledge of how chemicals induce adverse effects in humans and wildlife, using these Adverse Outcome Pathways. AOPs are therefore the central element of a toxicological knowledge framework being built to support chemical risk assessment based on mechanistic reasoning.

1.2. The AOP-Wiki

AOP Knowledge is created by parties (mostly researchers) who examine the scientific literature, extract the relevant information, organise it according to the AOP principles and capture it in the AOP-Wiki (<https://aopwiki.org/>), see Figure 2:

Figure 2 – The AOP development and assessment process

Current numbers concerning the AOP-Wiki (2024-09-11):

- 487 Adverse Outcome Pathways (AOP)
 - 1789 Key Events (KE)
 - 2822 Key Event Relationships (KER)
- 328 Users with Author privileges

2. THE ROLE OF AI IN THE AOP DOMAIN

2.1. Why AI is needed

2.1.1. AOP Development, Assessment and Review

The AOP development and assessment process shown in Figure 2 is very time-consuming, as an enormous number of literature references need to be read, quality-checked, and assessed. Relevant content needs to be extracted, and the selected knowledge must be translated into KEs, KERs, and assembled into an AOP, and the AOP needs to be assessed and reviewed.

As laid out in (OECD, 2018), the AOP development and assessment process consists four major steps:

1. AOP description:
The AOP description is entered on the upper portion of an AOP page within the AOP-Wiki. This is where some background information may be provided, the structure of the AOP is described, and the KEs and KERs are listed.
2. KE description:
Key Events announced in the AOP description need to be thoroughly described and their scientific background be elaborated.
3. KER description:
A KER description has to be created for each adjacent upstream-downstream pair of KEs in the pathway. Within the AOP framework, the

predictive relationships that facilitate extrapolation are represented by the Key Event Relationships. Consequently, the overall WoE for an AOP is a reflection in part, of the level of confidence in the underlying series of KERs it encompasses.

4. Overall AOP assessment:

The assessment is entered in the bottom part of the AOP-Wiki, and its goal is not to reproduce or reiterate all the content assembled as part of sections 1-3, but rather to provide a high level synthesis and overview of the relative confidence in the AOP and where the significant gaps or weaknesses are (if they exist).

These processes are currently supported by the comprehensive Users' Handbook (OECD, 2018)), a team of coaches and various groups and fora in which AOP developers can ask for support and get help.

5. In the context of this document, a fifth process must be included: The AOP review process, as laid out in (OECD, 2021), completes the picture: The scientific review of an AOP, is initiated after completion of the Users' Handbook compliance check by coaches and its ultimate goal is the endorsement of the AOP by the OECD.

The sheer effort required for humans to accomplish these tasks is often prohibitive, causing scientists to shy away from even considering developing an AOP. While the number of AOPs in the AOP-Wiki is still increasing and the AOP concept is now an established scientific concept, there is a risk that a critical mass of AOPs (which would herald a true paradigm shift in science) will not be reached unless a new approach supports a significant growth in AOP numbers.

The main problem of the AOP Framework is its **linear scaling**: When 2 AOPs require 10 scientists (and reviewers), then 200 AOPs require 1000 scientists (and reviewers) – and this is **not sustainable**.

It can be assumed that **AI can support many aspects of the AOP development, assessment and review process**.

2.1.2. Usage of AOPs

AOPs are obviously not an end in themselves but need to be found, read, accepted, understood and be applied to real-life (regulatory) purposes. Innovative ways should be explored in which AI can be leveraged to support the usage, understanding, and uptake of AOPs. From enhancing the usability of the AOP-Wiki to facilitating international collaboration through multilingual support, AI can be at the forefront of transforming AOP knowledge into a more dynamic and user-friendly resource. When AI intersects with AOPs, it can provide insights into how such technological advancements drive better decision-making in the fields of toxicology, risk assessment, and environmental health.

2.1.3. AOP Community building

The creation and advancement of the AOP framework is not solely a scientific endeavour but also one of community engagement and collaboration. The AOP community, consisting of researchers, regulators, and stakeholders from various

sectors, plays a critical role in the continuous development and application of AOP knowledge. However, building and maintaining a vibrant, collaborative, and efficiently functioning community presents its own set of challenges, from engaging stakeholders to fostering a culture of contribution and recognition.

Enter the transformative power of AI, which can offer a suite of hands-on applications capable of enhancing community building activities within the AOP ecosystem. There are diverse ways in which AI can support the AOP community by facilitating expert engagement, incentivizing contributions, and streamlining communication and collaboration efforts. These AI-driven processes not only aim to strengthen the ties between current community members but also to expand the reach of the AOP-Wiki and attract new experts and enthusiasts to the fold.

The integration of AI into community management strategies promises to accelerate the growth and cohesion of the AOP community, creating a more dynamic and inclusive environment where knowledge can be shared, challenges can be collectively addressed, and innovation can flourish. AI has the potential to revolutionize community interactions, enhance the user experience, and ultimately contribute to the robust development and review of AOPs as pointed out in section 2.1.1. Technology and human expertise should converge to advance our understanding and protection of human health and the environment.

2.2. AI4AOP – a crowd effort

AI4AOP will be an effort to explore the possibilities of using AI to support the key processes in the AOP domain, as laid out in 2.1. Ideally, a group of like-minded individuals will work together to leverage the power of AI to overcome the bottleneck of specialized expertise in creating a critical mass of AOPs.

The group will form, will select topics to be treated (using section 3 as a starting point) and will agree on desired goals and deliverables. Section 4 enumerates various possible short-term goals.

3. HOW AI CAN SUPPORT THE AOP FRAMEWORK

The AI4AOP effort should explore all areas and domains, processes, and workflows in which AI can support, simplify, or speed up the ideation, creation, maintenance, promotion and quality checking of AOPs. The following list is therefore non-exhaustive and only a thought starter for the start-up phase of the effort.

Each of the following processes leverages different aspects of AI technology, such as machine learning, deep learning, neural networks, and natural language processing, to support the various domains involved in AOP development and application. The main stakeholder communities that would benefit from these AI-supported processes include researchers, regulatory bodies, industry professionals, and educators, all of whom play a role in the safe management of chemicals and the protection of public health and the environment.

As also pointed out in (Wittwehr, et al., 2020), AI can *both* support the technical/scientific aspect of chemical risk assessment *and* the social/collaborative part. This applies obviously also to the ways AI can support the AOP framework.

3.1. AI supports AOP development, assessment and review

As laid out in 2.1.1, the AI support for the five processes (1) AOP description, (2) KE description, (3) KER description, (4) overall AOP assessment, as well as (5) AOP review is essential for scaling the AOP framework to the extent necessary to be fully embraced by the toxicology community.:

3.1.1. AI points out emerging issues to be covered by an AOP

- AI can monitor various data streams to identify new trends or emerging risks in toxicology and related fields. By analysing traditional media, social media, grey literature, and scientific publications, AI can highlight topics that may benefit from the development of new AOPs.
- Stakeholders in the scientific and regulatory communities would benefit from this foresight.
- Suitable AI: Natural Language Processing (NLP), trend analysis algorithms, and data mining techniques.

3.1.2. AI identifies relevant literature

- AI can assist researchers by sifting through vast databases of scientific literature to find relevant studies for a specific AOP. This can significantly reduce the time required for literature review.
- Again, stakeholders in the scientific and regulatory communities would benefit from this foresight.
- Suitable AI: Machine learning algorithms for text classification, NLP for semantic analysis, and information retrieval systems. Systems like vAST, LaserAI, Rayyan.

3.1.3. AI distils literature into KEs

- AI can process and extract pertinent information from identified literature to determine key events related to a toxicological issue. This can streamline the process of building AOPs by automating the extraction of mechanistic data. In addition, AI can help to extract methods that can be used to measure KEs.
- Stakeholders: Researchers, especially AOP authors.
- Suitable AI: Deep learning for pattern recognition, NLP for extracting structured information from unstructured text. Systems like SWIFTreview and DistillerSR.
- Identified initiatives already active: AOP-helpFinder 2.0¹

3.1.4. AI connects KEs and identifies KERs

- AI can analyse relationships between key events to suggest possible key event relationships, facilitating the construction of more comprehensive AOPs. This

¹ <https://aop-helpfinder.u-paris-sciences.fr/>

can help in understanding complex biological interactions, especially when identifying mechanisms (e.g. when upstream KE is overexpressed or inhibited, what happens to the downstream KE, including temporality). Metadata extraction can be harmonised by applying the same AI rules all over again.

- Stakeholders: Researchers, especially AOP authors.
- Suitable AI: Neural networks for identifying patterns and relationships, graph theory algorithms for mapping connections.
- Identified initiatives already active: AOP-helpFinder 2.0

3.1.5. AI for systematic review and evidence mapping

- AI can automate the process of systematic review, which is crucial for evaluating the quality and relevance of evidence for AOPs. Evidence mapping can be accelerated with AI, identifying gaps and informing future research priorities.
- Stakeholders: Researchers, regulatory bodies, and policy-makers.
- Suitable AI: Machine learning for systematic review automation, database querying algorithms.
- Identified initiatives already active:

3.1.6. AI for detecting AOP networks

- AI can be used to identify patterns in the scientific literature, but also in the AOP-Wiki, which would lead to the creation of AOP networks.
- Stakeholders: Toxicologists, risk assessors, regulatory agencies.
- Suitable AI: Neural networks for identifying patterns and relationships, graph theory algorithms for mapping connections.

3.1.7. AI-assisted data integration and harmonization

- AI can assist in integrating diverse data types (e.g., in vitro, in vivo, epidemiological data) to support AOP development, ensuring consistency and facilitating cross-study comparisons. As a first step AOP could help integrate in vitro data between studies; if metadata are correctly inserted, then AI could help to identify in vitro studies that can be compared (or not).
- Stakeholders: Data scientists, AOP developers, regulatory assessors.
- Suitable AI: Data fusion algorithms, ontologies, and semantic web technologies.

3.1.8. AI for facilitating peer review and consensus building

- AI can support the peer review process by matching submitted AOPs with potential reviewers, managing review workflows, and synthesizing feedback to help authors improve their submissions.
- Stakeholders: AOP authors, reviewers, journal editors.

- Suitable AI: Workflow automation tools, decision support systems.

3.2. AI supports AOP usage, understanding and uptake

Following up on section 2.1.2, the following AI-supported processes aim to enhance improve user interaction with the AOP knowledge.

3.2.1. AI for enhancing AOP-Wiki usability and interactivity

- AI can improve the user experience of the AOP-Wiki by providing intelligent search capabilities, personalized content recommendations, and interactive data visualizations.
- Stakeholders: AOP-Wiki users, educational institutions, researchers.
- Suitable AI: Recommender systems, user interface optimization algorithms.
- Already identified activities:
 - ChatAOP in the Harmless² project
 - JRC effort to create ChatGPT API to AOP-Wiki
 - *This* JRC initiative AI4AOP

3.2.2. AI in training and educational tools for AOP development

- AI can be used to develop training programs and educational materials that adapt to the user's learning pace and style, promoting wider adoption of the AOP framework.
- Stakeholders: Students, educators, early-career researchers.
- Suitable AI: Adaptive learning systems, educational bots.

3.2.3. AI for quality control and consistency checks in AOP development, including double KE entries

- AI can perform automated quality control by checking for inconsistencies or missing or overlapping information in AOP descriptions, ensuring high-quality entries in the AOP-Wiki. This includes the detection of overlapping, similar or outright double KEs. Fixing quality issues will go a long way in acceptance and uptake of AOP knowledge. While AOP development and assessment described in section 3.1 is done by a team working on a specific AOP development project, this process is a meta-analysis and refinement of the whole AOP knowledgebase done by ‘gardeners’ and the like.
- Stakeholders: AOP-Wiki editors, AOP-Wiki Gardeners, quality assurance teams.

² <https://www.harmless-project.eu/>

- Suitable AI: Consistency checking algorithms, anomaly detection systems.

3.2.4. AI for translation and multilingual support in AOP-Wiki

- AI can provide real-time translation and multilingual support to make AOP-Wiki accessible to a global audience, facilitating international collaboration.
- Stakeholders: Non-English-speaking researchers, international regulatory bodies.
- Suitable AI: Machine translation systems, cross-lingual information retrieval.

3.3. AI supports AOP community building

The following AI-supported processes aim to enhance community management by streamlining the identification and engagement of experts, tracking and rewarding contributions, and facilitating collaboration and communication within the AOP community. As pointed out in section 2.1.3, the use of AI in these areas can help build a more cohesive and active community around the AOP-Wiki, ultimately leading to more efficient and effective development and review of AOPs. Obviously many of these areas are not limited to the AOP domain, and input or feedback from other scientific disciplines will have to be sought.

3.3.1. AI for stakeholder engagement and community building

- AI can analyse user interaction data to identify key contributors and foster community engagement through targeted outreach and collaboration opportunities.
- Stakeholders: AOP-Wiki community managers, communication specialists.
- Suitable AI: Social network analysis, community detection algorithms.

3.3.2. AI for expert identification and engagement

- AI can analyse publication records, citation networks, and digital footprints to identify and recommend experts for peer review or collaboration on AOP development. This can help in assembling panels with the right mix of expertise for reviewing and contributing to AOPs.
- Stakeholders: AOP-Wiki administrators, workshop organizers, editorial boards.
- Suitable AI: Expertise discovery systems, network analysis algorithms.

3.3.3. AI for tracking contributions and recognizing expertise

- AI can track user contributions to the AOP-Wiki and other related platforms to recognize and reward active community members, which can encourage further participation and contribution. AI-powered “gamification” of AOP-related accomplishments could encourage new stakeholder communities to contribute.
- Stakeholders: AOP-Wiki contributors, professional societies, funding agencies.

- Suitable AI: Contribution tracking systems, reputation management algorithms.

3.3.4. AI for community-driven AOP curation and validation

- AI can facilitate community curation by prompting users to validate information, suggest edits, or contribute missing data, ensuring the AOP-Wiki remains accurate and up-to-date. To be seen in relation to 3.1.8 and 3.2.3.
- Stakeholders: AOP-Wiki curators, the broader scientific community.
- Suitable AI: Collaborative filtering, crowd-sourcing support tools.

3.3.5. AI for conflict resolution and consensus analysis

- AI can analyse discussions and debates within the community to identify points of contention or consensus, helping to guide discussions towards productive outcomes. Obviously, this aspect has to be monitored closely by humans.
- Stakeholders: AOP-Wiki moderators, AOP forum leaders.
- Suitable AI: Sentiment analysis, argument mining algorithms.

3.3.6. AI for personalized communication and updates

- AI can send personalized updates and notifications to community members about new AOPs, relevant literature, or collaboration opportunities based on their interests and expertise.
- Stakeholders: AOP-Wiki users, researchers, regulatory professionals.
- Suitable AI: Personalization engines, content recommendation systems.

3.3.7. AI for virtual collaboration and workshop facilitation

- AI can assist in organizing virtual workshops or collaborative sessions by managing invitations, scheduling, and follow-ups, as well as facilitating online discussions and brainstorming activities.
- Stakeholders: Workshop organizers, virtual event participants.
- Suitable AI: Virtual assistant bots, scheduling optimization algorithms.

4. POSSIBLE ROADMAP

4.1. General setup

The AI4AOP effort can build on previous experiences with crowdsourcing efforts, such as the CIAO project or the Methods2AOP collaboration. In efforts like these, participants agree on a common goal, contribute their time (in-kind), and produce an agreed outcome (e.g., one or several peer-reviewed papers).

AI4AOP should serve as a focal point for AI-related activities around AOPs, interacting with the AOP-KB CG and other groups coordinated by the CG:

Figure 3 - AI4AOP as one of several efforts shaping AOP-Wiki

4.2. Next steps

The AI4AOP effort should aim at the following short term goals:

Activity	Expected outcome
Reach out to members of a team joining the effort.	Establishment of a team that moves the effort forward. Agreement on rules that could govern the collaboration.
Further elaborate on expected outcome, expectations, resources, technical requirements.	More concrete vision & list of expected deliverables.
Decide on which third party AI know-how sources to tap into.	List of desired third parties with AI know-how.
Reach out to the identified third party AI know-how resources.	Possible partnership with third party AI know-how specialist..
Decide on outreach strategy.	Decision on who to involve for feedback, input etc. (SKIG, OECD, ...).
Identify ongoing pre-existing AI initiatives in the AOP domain (and related).	Clear vision on how to merge with other initiatives or where interfaces and synergies to such initiatives can be built.
Define scope of project, select aspects (starting point see section 3) to be examined.	More concrete plan about which aspects of the AOP domain should be supported by AI, what priorities should AI4AOP have.

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